

Exploring Traditional Knowledge : Bridging Past and Future

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Indian/Traditional knowledge system study in India is dominated by text based studies. A number of monographs and countless research papers have been published on the topic covered in this lecture on the basis of textual information (Hindu, Jain and Buddhist including secular orientation). I am not repeating the same in this lecture.

The address focuses mainly on the following points:

1. Need to study Traditional Knowledge system
2. Traditional health care system
3. Areas of study in northeast India

One of the aspects of colonial historiography was to undermine/play the historical progresses in India in the field of science technology and medicine. The political supremacy was often combined with the social and cultural supremacy and the "Whiteman's Burden" theory. So the study of Indian science, technology and medicine was at the one hand neglected and on the other termed as myth, magic, etc. Even after the Independence of India in 1947, the researches on tribal technology and its social implications have never seriously been on the agenda of the social science researchers. This is because they inherited not only the concepts, techniques, theories and methods of study but also the subjects of study from early (colonial) ethnographers. Nonetheless, the influence and impact of their approaches, trends and findings are still felt on the study of tribal technology. This, clearly, is the colonial hangover that still ails some of the historians and social scientists.

In recent past, efforts have been made to study history of science, technology and medicine in India. However, the condition of research in northeast India in this field is not very encouraging. And many more efforts like this have to be done to reconstruct the history of India.